

VEHICLE DAMAGE ASSESSMENT SYSTEM

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Abstract— The utilization of machine learning algorithms for object detection plays a vital role in various applications, including damage assessment in automotive industries. This paper focuses on the implementation of YOLOv5, a state-of-the-art object detection model, for detecting and categorizing damages in vehicle images. The primary objective is to assist automobile inspectors and insurance companies in accurately identifying damages such as scratches, deformations, broken glass, and breakage. By leveraging YOLOv5, the proposed system provides real-time detection and localization of damages, enabling efficient assessment of vehicle conditions. Furthermore, a pricing mechanism is integrated based on the severity of damages detected, aiding in the estimation of repair costs.

Keywords— damage, object detection, image processing, yolo.

I. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, the integration of machine learning algorithms has revolutionized various industries, offering efficient solutions to complex problems. One such application lies in object detection, where algorithms like YOLOv5 have emerged as state-of-the-art models capable of accurately detecting and categorizing objects in images or video frames. In particular, the automotive industry stands to benefit significantly from the implementation of these technologies, especially in the realm of damage assessment.

This paper aims to introduce an approach to damage assessment in the automotive sector by leveraging the power of YOLOv5 for object detection. The primary objective is to develop a system that can automatically detect and categorize damages in vehicle images, thereby assisting automobile inspectors and insurance companies in their assessment processes. The damages targeted for detection include scratches, deformations, broken glass, and breakage, which are common occurrences in vehicle accidents or incidents.

By employing YOLOv5, the proposed system offers real-time detection and localization of damages, allowing for swift and accurate evaluation of vehicle conditions. Unlike traditional manual inspection methods, which can be time-consuming and subjective, this automated approach enhances efficiency and reduces human error. Moreover, the integration of a pricing mechanism based on the severity of damages detected enables the estimation of repair costs, providing valuable insights for insurance claims and repair services.

Overall, this project aims to address the challenges associated with damage assessment in the automotive industry by harnessing the capabilities of advanced machine learning techniques. Through the implementation of YOLOv5, this

project seek to offer a reliable and efficient solution that not only streamlines the inspection process but also enhances the accuracy and fairness of damage evaluation. The following sections will delve into the methodology, experimentation, results, highlighting its potential impact on the automotive sector.

II. RELATED WORKS

- A. In the article [1] the authors develop a tiny object detection model based on a competitive multi-layer neural network (TOD-CMLNN). The model is designed to efficiently detect small objects, offering potential applications in various fields such as computer vision and robotics.
- B. The paper [2] presents a method for binarization and classification of ancient epic manuscripts using false color spectralization techniques and the VGG-16 deep learning model. The approach aims to enhance the preservation and analysis of historical documents through advanced image processing and classification methods.
- C. Researchers in this paper [3] focus on the design and development of a coffee machine control system utilizing fuzzy logic techniques. The system aims to enhance the precision and adaptability of coffee brewing processes, offering improved user experience and quality of coffee production.
- D. The paper [4] conducts a performance comparison of supervised learning methods, specifically comparing non-neural network algorithms with neural network-based approaches. The study evaluates the effectiveness and efficiency of different learning techniques in various applications, providing insights into the strengths and limitations of each approach.
- E. The research in this paper [5] focuses on disease classification on rice leaves using DenseNet architectures including DenseNet121, DenseNet169, and DenseNet201. The study aims to accurately identify and classify diseases affecting rice crops, offering potential applications in precision agriculture and crop management.
- F. The paper [6] reevaluates the PASCAL-VOC and MS-COCO datasets for small object detection tasks. The study proposes improvements and modifications to existing datasets to better suit the requirements of small object detection algorithms, contributing to the advancement of object detection research in computer vision.

- G. The study explores the application of convolutional neural networks (CNNs) for vehicle damage detection. By employing CNNs, the research [7] aims to develop a robust and efficient system capable of automatically detecting and analyzing damage to vehicles, offering potential applications in insurance claims processing and automotive safety.
- H. [8] This research investigates a lightweight YOLO (You Only Look Once) algorithm for coal gangue detection, utilizing a ResNet18 backbone feature network. The study aims to develop an efficient and accurate system for detecting coal gangue in mining environments, contributing to improved safety and productivity in the coal mining industry.

III. METHODOLOGY

This system implements an object detection and cost estimation system using the YOLOv5 model. Aims to detect various damages in images and estimate the repair costs associated with each detected object. Identifies objects of interest and annotates them with bounding boxes and labels. Leveraging a variety of Python libraries such as PIL, TensorFlow, and PyTorch, and this system enables users to upload images, detect objects, and estimate repair costs associated with identified damages.

A. Image Preprocessing:

Upon receipt of a POST request containing an image file, utilizes the PIL library to read the file's bytes and subsequently converts the image to JPEG format. This preprocessing step ensures compatibility with the YOLOv5 model, which requires images in a specific format for effective inference.

```
if request.method == "POST":
    if "file" not in request.files:
        return redirect(request.url)
    file = request.files["file"]
    if not file:
        return
    img_bytes = file.read()
    img_path = convert_image_to_jpeg(img_bytes)
    img = Image.open(img_path)
```

B. Object Detection :

Leveraging the trained YOLOv5 model and conducts object detection on the uploaded image. This process entails annotating detected objects with bounding boxes and labels, providing users with valuable insights into the types and locations of damages present within the image.

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```
results = model(img)
results.render()
```

C. Damage Labeling and Cost Estimation

Detected objects are cross-referenced with a predefined damage label dictionary, allowing for the identification of various damages such as scratches, deformations, broken glass, and more. Additionally, confidence scores associated with each detection are leveraged to estimate repair costs, providing users with a comprehensive understanding of the potential financial implications.

```
price_dict = {
    'Scratch': 750,
    'Deformation': 1500,
    'Broken Glass': 5000,
    'Broken': 40000
}

for obj, confidence, label in detected_objects_with_scores:
    if label in price_dict:
        price = price_dict[label]
        price_with_confidence = round(price * confidence, 2)
        total_price += price_with_confidence
        detected_objects_with_prices.append((obj, confidence, label, price_with_confidence))
```

D. Merging Images and Rendering Results:

Annotated images generated from the object detection step are merged with the original image to visualize the detected objects and their associated damages. Results, including the merged image, detected objects, and estimated repair costs, are rendered to the user interface.

```
return render_template("display_image.html",
    image_path="static/images/image0.jpg",
    detected_objects_with_scores=detected_objects_with_prices,
    total_price=round(total_price))
```

E. Deployment:

The server is subsequently deployed, allowing it to listen for incoming requests and facilitate seamless interactions between users and our deep learning-powered object detection system

IV. RESULT

fig 1. User Interface

fig 2. Output

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this paper has presented an innovative approach to damage assessment within the automotive industry, leveraging the capabilities of YOLOv5 for object detection and categorization. By automating the process of detecting damages such as scratches, deformations, broken glass, and breakage in vehicle images, the proposed system offers significant benefits to automobile inspectors, insurance companies, and repair services.

Through real-time detection and localization of damages, the system enables swift and accurate evaluation of vehicle conditions, reducing the time and subjectivity associated with manual inspection methods. Additionally, the integration of a pricing mechanism based on the severity of damages detected facilitates the estimation of repair costs, providing valuable insights for insurance claims and repair services.

The potential impact of this work on improving efficiency, reducing costs, and enhancing customer satisfaction in the

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automotive sector is substantial, paving the way for future advancements in automated damage assessment technologies.

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